

SUMMARY

TOWARDS A THEORY OF MANAGEMENT

The writer discusses the first chapter of the book: "Human Relations and Modern Management" (Amsterdam 1958), called "Human Relations and Fundamental Principles of Management", written by Prof. Dr. J. L. Mey, Groningen. He also includes in his discussion articles which Prof. J. L. Mey has published since 1952 in various periodicals at home and abroad. The reason for this is to be found in the fact that all these articles are intended as contributions to new theoretical considerations on the fundamental principles of the theory of organization. His study "Human Relations and Modern Management", however, refers these considerations no longer to a theory of organization but to a theory of management.

Against the traditional theory of organization Prof. J. L. Mey raises the objection that it "has not been built around any general frame of reference but has rather emerged as a series of principles of administration".

As appears from his studies in the various periodicals Prof. J. L. Mey now sees as the central fundamental principle for a theory of organization the deepening and widening of the scope of control. Scope of control has a wider sense than span of control, it does however include span of control. The reviewer raises objections against this doctrine, because various phenomena of organization cannot be explained from the principle of the deepening and widening, e.g. the centralization tendencies with the introduction of a big computer. These tendencies should be explained from the principles of the relations of quantity and geographical place according to the reviewer.

The Amsterdam Prof. Dr. Th. Limperg therefore bases the theory of organization in a more satisfactory way on two groups of principles, i.e.

1. on the comparative relations (of quantity, place, time, power, right, interest);
2. on the principle of the deepening and widening of the scope of control.

Though the principle of deepening and widening is inadequate for a *theory of organization*. This does not apply, according to the reviewer when a distinction is made in principle between management and organization and when the principle of deepening and widening is consciously presented as a theory of management. In the reviewer's opinion the principle of the deepening and widening of the scope of control and the working out as in the article in "Human Relations and Modern Management" are certainly of importance in that case. It should be remembered that the principle does not give a complete theory of management, but constitutes a building stone for such a theory.

The reviewer points out that Prof. J. L. Mey has not discussed some important elements for the widening and deepening of the scope of control.

A.o. policy formulation and management development.

To conclude with he thinks, that fitting problems the concerning human relations into the theory of deepening and widening is more complicated than might be inferred from the considerations of Prof. J. L. Mey in view of the fact that management, organization and human relations cannot and should not be considered as separate quantities but in their interdependent relation. In various cases an improvement of the human relations depends on different methods of organization or on a different structure of organization. With reference to this the reviewer points to the problems of the "tall" or "flat" organizational structure and to the subjects discussed in the other articles in the book, a.o. in that by Prof. R. W. Revans: "Human Relations, Management and Size".

In a subsequent article the other chapters will be dealt with.